

Hossein Barani-Beiranvand
CURRICULUM VITAE

Academic Information

Dr. Hossein Barani-Beiranvand

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Schooling 1992 - 1995

High School Diploma in Experimental Sciences
Imam Khomeini High School, Khorramabad, Iran

University Education

PhD in Biology (Animal Biosystematics) 2010 - 2016

Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran

Promoters: Prof. Mansour Aliabadian & Prof. Tamás Székely (University of Bath, UK)

Thesis: Investigating the taxonomic status and biogeography of Penduline Tits (*Remiz pendulinus*) in Iran (morphological, molecular and behavioral data)

Date of Defense: 14 Feb 2017

Master Degree in Biology (Zoology, Biosystematics) 2000 – 2003

Shiraz University, Shiraz, Iran

Thesis: Biodiversity study of aquatic Coleoptera in Chahar-cheshmeh spring-stream system, Bamoo National Park

Bachelor Degree in Biology (Zoology) 1995 - 1999

Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran

Research Project: Aquatic insects of Karde Basin (Khorasan-Iran)

Teaching Experience

Farhangian University, Isfahan 2023 - Present

- Cell Biology
- Genetics
- Animal Biology
- Invertebrate Zoology
- Vertebrate Zoology

Azad University of Najafabad, Isfahan 2017 - 2023

- Cell Biology
- Bioinformatics
- Genetics
- Animal Biology
- Zoology

Science and Culture University, Tehran (Visiting Lecturer) 2018 - 2019

- General Biology
- Principles of Zoology

Azad University of Mashhad, Mashhad (Visiting Lecturer) 2010 - 2017

- Vertebrate Zoology
- Principles of Zoology
- Animal Physiology
- Evolution
- Parasitology
- Protozoology
- Entomology

Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Mashhad 2010 - 2013

- Vertebrate Zoology
- Molecular Systematics
- Species and Speciation
- Animal Systematics

Azad University of Khorramabad, Lorestan 2004 - 2010

- General Biology
- Biogeography
- Principles of Zoology
- Evolution
- Environment
- Animal Physiology
- Molecular Genetics and Evolution
- Graduate Seminar

Student Advisement

Master Students

- Masume Asadi, Guilan University, 2010
- Ehsan Foruzanfar, Azad University Ahvaz, 2012
- Nafise Sheibany, Shahre-kord University, 2021

PhD Students

- Elham Madadi, Shahre-kord University, 2021
- Ali Nasiri, Shahre-kord University, 2023

Scientific Skills

- Morphological variation analysis: Traditional biometry (EXCEL, SPSS, STATISTICA, PAST) and geometric morphometrics (TPS, IMAGEJ, MORPHOJ, PAST)
 - Molecular phylogeny and phylogeography: PHYLIP, PHYML, MEGA, MRBAYES
 - Population genetics and demographic history: DNASP, Popart, Genepop, GenAIEx, Arlequin, STRUCTURE
 - Ecological niche and distribution modeling: ARC-GIS, MaxEnt, ENMTools, RANGEMODEL
 - Experienced in teaching general biology and mentoring undergraduate/graduate research
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Professional Experience

- **2023-Present:** Director, Department of Basic Sciences, Farhangian University, Isfahan
 - **2017-2023:** Director, Department of Biological Science and Technology, Azad University of Najafabad
 - **2014:** Research Collaborator, Swedish Museum of Natural History (NRM), Sweden
 - **2005-2009:** Graduate Assistant, Department of Biology, Shiraz University
 - **2001-2004:** Undergraduate Assistant, Department of Biology, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad
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Scientific Lectures and Workshops

Lectures

- The Origin of Life (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2007)
- What is Biodiversity (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2007)
- Animal Behavioral Studies (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2008)
- Iran's Wildlife (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2009)
- Biogeography (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2009)
- Global Warming and the Phenomenon of El Niño (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2010)
- Life History on Earth – Vertebrates Model (Azad University, Khorramabad, 2017)

Workshops

Animal Taxidermy Workshop, Ferdowsi University (2011)

- DNA Barcoding Workshop, Ferdowsi University (2011)
 - Environmental Crisis on Earth Day, Azad University Najafabad (2019)
 - An introduction to NCBI, Farhangian University (2024)
 - From Cell to Meaning, Farhangian University (2024)
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External Services

- Member, Iranian Biology Society (IBS) since 2004
 - Reviewer for Journal of Genetic Resources
 - Reviewer for Journal of Animal Diversity
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Grants

- European Community Sixth Framework Programme (GEBACO FP6/2002-2006), contract 28696
 - Ferdowsi University of Mashhad Grant (2013)
 - Ministry of Science, Iran Grant (2014) with Prof. Mansur Aliabadian
 - Candidate, American Philosophical Society's Lewis and Clark Fund (2017)
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Internship and Work Experience

- Biology Student Society, Ferdowsi University (1996-1998)
- Internship: Passeriform birds project, Ferdowsi University (1997-1999)
- Biosystematics Lab of Prof. Jamshid Darvish (6 months, 1998-1999)
- Biology Tutor in high schools of Mashhad, Shiraz, Isfahan (1996-2003)
- Biology Student Society, Shiraz University (2001-2002)
- Biology and Zoology Tutor, Shiraz and Azad University of Jahrom (2001-2003)

- Student Assistant, Shiraz University (2001-2003)
- Cooperation in IUCN Project on *Neurergus kaiseri* (2003-2008)
- Project on *Asaccus griseonotus* (2007-2010)
- Project on *Remiz pendulinus* (2013-2015)
- Project on Raptors in Lorestan (2016-2018)

Books and Teaching Materials

- Translator Board Member, “Integrated Principles of Zoology” (Hickman et al.), Tehran Biology House (2018)
- Compilation of teaching notebooks for university courses (1996-2023)
- Practical biology laboratory teaching in Isfahan schools (2022-2023)
- Inventor of “Biology for Kids” teaching method in Isfahan (2022-2023)
- Teaching Biology Olympiad based on Campbell Biology (2016-2023)

Research Interests

- Molecular systematics and phylogenetics
- Biogeography and behavioral ecology
- Speciation and diversification
- Bioinformatics applications in medicine, agriculture, pharmaceuticals
- Using AI in phylogeny and evolutionary problems

References and Conference Papers

Journal Articles

- Nasiri, A., Fallah, S., Sadeghpour, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2024). Assessing the potential of Fedaleh (*Echinophora cinerea*) essential oils as a natural herbicide for spring–summer crops. *Heliyon*, 10(16), e36085. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e36085>
- Madadi, E., Fallah, S., Sadeghpour, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2023). Black cumin bioactive compounds as eco-friendly novel green herbicides in wheat cropping: Application to reduce chemical herbicides pollution. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-023-04980-z>
- Madadi, E., Fallah, S., Sadeghpour, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2023). The effect of allelochemical compounds of chamomile on changes in physiological parameters and growth of charlock mustard compared to wheat. *Journal of Iranian Society of Plant Physiology*, 11(47), 173–194. <http://jispp.iut.ac.ir/article-1-1567-fa.html>
- Madadi, E., Fallah, S., Sadeghpour, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2022). Exploring the use of chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) bioactive compounds to control flixweed (*Descurainia sophia* L.) in bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.): Implications for reducing chemical herbicide pollution. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 29(11), 103421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2022.103421>
- Madadi, E., Fallah, S., Sadeghpour, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2022). Effects of *Nigella sativa* allelochemical substances on growth inhibition of flixweed compared with wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). *Journal of Crop Production and Processing*, 12(3), 49–66. <http://jcphp.iut.ac.ir/article-1-3148-fa.html>

- Sheibany, N., Fallah, S., Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Salehi, A. (2022). Effect of feeding soybean with different concentrations of zinc compounds on germination of produced seed and initial seedling growth. *Iranian Journal of Seed Science and Technology*, 11(2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ijssst.2022.356183.1411>
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., Aliabadian, M., Rabii, K., & van Dijk, R. E. (2018). Breeding biology of Black-headed Penduline Tit (*Remiz macronyx neglectus*) in northern Iran. *Bird Study*. [Submitted]
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., Aliabadian, M., Irestedt, M., Qu, Y., Darvish, J., Székely, T., van Dijk, R. E., & Ericson, P. G. P. (2017). Phylogeography of Eurasian Penduline Tits inferred from mitochondrial and microsatellite genotyping. *Journal of Avian Biology*, 48(7), 932–940. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jav.01163>
- Haddadian Shad, H., Darvish, J., Mohammadian, T., Mahmoudi, A., Alaie-Kakhki, N., Ghanbarifardi, M., Molavi, F., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2014). Preliminary study of rodents using pellets of predatory birds in Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics*, 10(1), 36–50.
- Rabii, K., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2015, August 18–24). A study of wintering wetland-dependent waterbirds in Mazandaran Province. XIV International Ornithological Conference of North Eurasia, Almaty, Kazakhstan, 572–573.
- Amiri, M., Musivand, M., Ghaedrahmati, N., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2015, August 18–24). A survey on wintering waterbirds in Pol-e Dokhtar wetlands, Lorestan Province. XIV International Ornithological Conference of North Eurasia, Almaty, Kazakhstan, 569.
- Sharifi, M., Farasat, H., Barani-Beiranvand, H., Vaissi, S., Foroozanfar, E., & Browne, R. (2014). Notes on the distribution and abundance of the endangered Kaiser’s Mountain Newt *Neurergus kaiseri* (Caudata: Salamandridae) in southwestern Iran. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology*, 8(3), 724–731.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Aliabadian, M. (2012). Distribution and taxonomic issues of Penduline Tits in Iran based on Zarudny’s collections. In *Terrestrial vertebrates of arid ecosystems (Dedicated to the memory of N.A. Zarudny)*. National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
- Aliabadian, M., Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Ghasempouri, S. M. (2012). Expeditions of N. A. Zarudny in Iran (Persia). In *Terrestrial vertebrates of arid ecosystems (Dedicated to the memory of N.A. Zarudny)*. National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
- Ghasempouri, S. M., Aliabadian, M., Kiabi, B. H., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2012). Systematic status of *Oenanthe pleschanka vittata* (Hemprich et Ehrenberg, 1833) based on morphological data. In *Terrestrial vertebrates of arid ecosystems (Dedicated to the memory of N.A. Zarudny)*. National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
- Molavi, F., Ghanbari-Fardi, M., Mohammadian-Kalat, T., Hadadian, H., Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Aliabadian, M. (2012). Investigation of factors affecting patterns of *Rana* genus distribution in Iran using SAM (Spatial Analysis in Macroecology). *Journal of Animal Biology*, 5(1). [In Persian]
- Rajabizadeh, M., Rastegar-Pouyani, N., Khosravani, A., Barani-Beiranvand, H., Faizi, H., & Oraei, H. (2010). New records of two lacertid genera, *Iranolacerta* and *Apathya* (Sauria: Lacertidae) in Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics*, 6(2), 21–32.

Conference Papers & Presentations

- Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2016, September). Conservation study of raptors according to national and international conservation rules in Lorestan Province. In Proceedings of the 2nd National Conference of Biological Sciences. Islamic Azad University, Damghan Branch, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., Amiri, H., Ghaedrahmati, N., & Rushani, A. (2016, September). Distribution of Accipitriformes and Falconiformes in Lorestan Province. In Proceedings of the 2nd National Conference of Biological Sciences. Islamic Azad University, Damghan Branch, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., Darvish, J., & Aliabadian, M. (2014, August). Evaluation of the breeding and wintering sites of *Remiz pendulinus* complex species (Aves: Remizidae) in Iran. In Proceedings of the 18th National and 6th International Conference of Biology. Kharazmi University, Tehran, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2013, June). Conservation of biodiversity in Central Zagros as a base for ecotourism. In Proceedings of the 7th National Conference of Environment (World Environment Day). University of Tehran, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Haghi, A. (2012, September). A review and critique of the philosophical view of Mathias Gutmann on the role of structure and function in evolutionary reconstruction (Model: Arthropoda). In Proceedings of the 1st Iranian Integrated Zoological Conference. Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
- Aryan-mal, M. Sh., Jafari, M. H., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2011, May). The trend of taxonomic studies based on DNA barcoding in Afghanistan. In Proceedings of the 1st Conference on the Status of DNA Barcoding in Taxonomy. Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
- Ghodskhah Daryaii, M., Asadi, M., Jalali Sendi, J., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2010, October). Biology and nourishment indexes of *Lymantria dispar* (Lepidoptera) on four different jungle tree species. In Proceedings of the National Conference on Natural Resources: Harm and Challenges, Practical Research and Solutions. Ilam University, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Sharifi, M. (2010, August). Habitats and conservation of Lorestan newt (*Neurergus kaiseri*) in southwest Lorestan Province. In Proceedings of the 16th National and 4th International Conference of Biology. Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Torki, F. (2010, August). Spermatogenesis in *Asaccus griseonotus* (Reptilia: Gekkonidae) during spring in mountains around Khorramabad District, Lorestan, Iran. In Proceedings of the 16th National and 4th International Conference of Biology. Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Iran.
- Tavakoli, M., Piruzi, F., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2010, March). An introduction to oak seed insects in forest areas of Lorestan Province. In Proceedings of the 2nd Regional Conference on the Study of Protecting Natural Resources in Lorestan Province. Payame Noor University of Lorestan, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2008, August). Birds, past to present! *Bralik Journal*, Ministry of Education Publication, 1, Spring 2006.
- Amiri, M., Gharzi, A., & Barani-Beiranvand, H. (2008, July). Histology of ovary and oviduct in Lorestan salamander (*Neurergus kaiseri*). In Proceedings of the 15th National and 3rd International Conference of Biology. University of Tehran, Iran.

- Barani-Beiranvand, H., Hosseini (Ostovani), Sh., & Hosseini, F. (2005, August). Investigating the biodiversity of the aquatic Coleoptera fauna of spring-stream systems in Bamoo National Park, Shiraz, Iran. In Proceedings of the 13th National and 1st International Conference of Biology. University of Guilan, Iran.
- Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Aliabadian, M. (2002, July). Aquatic insects of Karde Basin (Khorasan, Iran). In Proceedings of the 1st National Conference of Biology and Biotechnology Students. University of Tehran, Iran.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5736893>
- Tavakoli, M., Barani-Beiranvand, H., & Sepahvand, K. (2002, September). Fauna of Satyridae (Lepidoptera) in jungles and natural landscapes of Lorestan Province. In Proceedings of the 15th Iranian Plant Protection Congress. Razi University of Kermanshah, Iran.